

Exploring Hyperbolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework

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Abstract: This study delves into the fascinating world of hyperbolas within the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) [11][15], providing a thorough understanding of the intricate connections between prime numbers, integers, and their divisors. It harmoniously complements and interweaves with the preceding study, titled "Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) [7]," collectively unveiling the existence of at least two prime numbers between any two consecutive positive square numbers.

Keywords: Integers and their divisors; pair of complementary divisors; factors; hyperbolas.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: 11A05; 11D09.

Discovering something new in mathematics is akin to arriving at a bustling train station amidst chaos, only to unexpectedly catch the distant sound of an orchestra playing Ravel's 'Boléro' continuously. Your perception of this musical masterpiece relies on both your distance from the orchestra and the specific part of the 'Boléro' being performed.

In mathematics, the threshold of your perception parallels the experience of following the unfolding melody of the 'Boléro'. It depends on your proximity to the idea and the phase of exploration at which you encounter it. Once the 'Boléro' captures your attention, it resonates within your mind until its very end.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Abbreviations and Definitions:

- $(d_{c1}; d_{c2})$: Denotes the central pair of complementary divisors such that $x \geq d_{c2} \geq +\sqrt{|x|} \geq d_{c1} \geq 1$, where $d_{c1} * d_{c2} = x = \text{positive integer}$.
- d_{c1} : Denotes the smallest central complementary divisor satisfying $d_{c2} \geq \pm\sqrt{|x|} \geq d_{c1}$, where $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$. For positive divisors, d_{c1} corresponds to the sequence at <https://oeis.org/A033676>.
- d_{c2} : Denotes the largest central complementary divisor satisfying $d_{c2} \geq \pm\sqrt{|x|} \geq d_{c1}$, and $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$. For positive divisors, d_{c2} corresponds to the sequence at <https://oeis.org/A033677>.
- b_{dm} : Defined as $b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$ saying the difference between the divisors of the central pair of complementary divisors. The sequence for b_{dm} can be found at <https://oeis.org/A056737>.

$$b_{dm} = \text{https://oeis.org/A033677}[x] - \text{https://oeis.org/A033676}[x] = \text{https://oeis.org/A056737}$$

- b_d : Defined as $b_d = d_2 - d_1$ saying the difference between the divisors of the pair of complementary divisors.

1.2 Reference and Further Reading:

The most recent notations in all studies, texts, figures, tables, graphs, etc., are available online at <https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/653023753021234/> or via the link <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10127987>.

To get an animated overview of the findings from this study, please refer to C000705 Hyperbolas in MID at <https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/permalink/310943667229246>.

2 Complementary Divisors in Diagonal Lines and Hyperbolas Interrelation

In the 1st quadrant of the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice grid (MHL) [15], each largest complementary divisor $d_2 \geq \sqrt{x}$ is positioned over the diagonal line $x = n * y$, where the angular coefficient n is an integer. The diagonal is outside the parabolic equation $x = y^2$ in the XY-plane. These largest divisors will multiply their smallest complementary divisors $d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$, for $x = d_1 * d_2$. All d_1 divisors in the 1st quadrant, are situated along the horizontal rows y equals n within the parabola.

Visualizing these concepts within the MHL lattice in table format:

Figure 1. [C000340](#) Highlights the depiction of points from the Map of Integers and their Divisors (MID) [15][11] represented in the MHL table format as dark green points.

In the 1st quadrant, above each SOM zone [9], there will be ascending diagonals $x = n * y$ representing $d_2 \geq \sqrt{x}$.

Inside each SOM zone, there will be further ascending diagonals representing $d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$.

Using the MID's X-axis as the reference for $x = d_1 * d_2$, each integer on the X-axis has pairs of complementary divisors aligned vertically. The smallest complementary divisors $1 \leq d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$ are closest to the X-axis, while the largest complementary divisors $\sqrt{x} \leq d_2 \leq x$ are positioned farthest away. The boundary for separation between them is $\sqrt{x}$.

3 Characterizing SOM Zones and Their Recurring Pattern

The Map of Integers and Divisors (MID), produced by the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice (MHL), provides a visual representation of the relationships between integers and their divisors. Within the MID, the SOM zones stand out as distinct regions that exhibit an intriguing pattern.

3.1 SOM Zone Definition

A SOM zone is defined as the region within the MID that encompasses divisors $d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$, where x is the integer in the X-axis. There are infinitely many SOM zones. Each SOM zone is bounded by a vertical line in $x = n^2$ position and another vertical line in the next (square-1) number, or $x = n^2 + 2n$. Exactly at the midpoint, there exists the vertical line $x = n^2 + n$ corresponding to an oblong number.

3.2 SO and OM Zones

Within each SOM zone, two subregions emerge: the SO zone and the OM zone. The SO zone encompasses divisors $d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$ between a square number and the next oblong number. Conversely, the OM zone encompasses divisors $d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$ between an oblong number and the next (square-1) number.

3.3 Recurring Pattern within SOM Zones

An intriguing characteristic of the MID is the recurring pattern observed within each SOM zone. This pattern entails the duplication of both the SO and OM zones within the broader SOM zone. This duplication results in a nested structure, where each SOM zone comprises two isomorphic internal zones—SO and OM—of identical size.

The recurring pattern within SOM zones suggests a deep-seated connection between the properties of integers and their divisors. This pattern highlights the self-similarity that exists within the MID, where larger structures exhibit the same patterns as their smaller counterparts.

3.4 Continuous Mosaic

The recurring pattern within SOM zones is so well-defined that if the area of one SOM zone did not increase quadratically in relation to another, it would form a continuous mosaic. This observation underscores the orderly nature of MID.

The SOM zones and their recurring pattern represent a fascinating aspect of the MID. This pattern provides insights into the structure of integers and their divisors, revealing a hidden order within the distribution of numbers. Further exploration of this pattern could lead to new discoveries in the realm of number theory and related fields.

Figure 2. C001640 Displaying the typical recurring pattern of a SOM zone in MID.

For a broader perspective on the recurring pattern of SOM zones, refer to <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=643105&postcount=20> or <https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/264911088499171/>, which contain larger tables providing detailed insights.

3.5 Recurrent Pattern of SOM Zones and Prime Number Distribution

The figure above depicts a typical SOM zone, illustrating the worst-case scenario where at least one prime number exists in both the SO and OM zones.

In the MID representation, there is no space between the numerical line on the X-axis and the SOM region that we have intentionally inserted here to facilitate the visualization of the distribution of divisors $d_1 \leq \sqrt{x}$ along the SO and OM zones.

Based on the observations in "Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework" [7] and "Divisor Trek," [11] all squares y^2 , oblongs $y^2 + y$, and (square-1) $y^2 + 2y$ inevitably contain the divisor y . Simultaneously, the distance between squares y^2 , oblongs $y^2 + y$, and (square-1) $y^2 + 2y$ is always y units.

Consequently, no number between a square y^2 and the oblong $y^2 + y$, or between an oblong $y^2 + y$ and the following (square-1) $y^2 + 2y$, contains the divisor y .

Within each SOM zone, only the square numbers y^2 , the oblongs $y^2 + y$, and the (square-1) $y^2 + 2y$ can have y as a divisor.

Thus, this study aims to demonstrate that in the MID, all integers on the X-axis exhibit the following properties:

- For any SO or OM zone, there are at most $y - 1$ divisors for y positions.
- At least one position in each SO or OM zone must have only one divisor $d_1 = 1$. This directly produces at least one prime number in SO zone and another OM zone.

The primes in the SO zone are listed in the OEIS sequence <https://oeis.org/A307508> (note that prime 1 is missing)[12], while the primes in the OM zone are listed in the OEIS sequence <https://oeis.org/A334163>.

By understanding this inherent pattern within the MID, we gain a deeper understanding of the distribution of prime numbers and their relationship to the structure of integers and their divisors.

4 Inherent Symmetry of the MID

The Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) exhibits a remarkable symmetry in the distribution of divisors along both the X and Y axes, with the origin (0,0) serving as the center of symmetry. This symmetry is depicted in Figure 3, where the arrangement of divisors is perfectly mirrored around the origin.

Figure 3. illustrates the complete symmetry of divisors within the MID around the origin (0,0).

4.1 Symmetry Propagation

The symmetry of divisors around the origin $(0,0)$ extends along the X-axis, and this symmetry is reflected in the divisor set of each integer. For every integer n represented as $n = d_1d_2$, the same sequence pattern of complementary divisors d_1 and d_2 appears along the vertical axis and the two $\pm 45^\circ$ diagonals.

Divisors along the vertical lines follow the equation: $x = n$.

Divisors along the $+45^\circ$ diagonals follow the equation: $x = y + n$.

Divisors along the -45° diagonals follow the equation: $x = -y + n$.

The figure below illustrates this pattern for the integer $n = 12$.

Figure 4. $\pm 45^\circ$ diagonals and the vertical of the divisors of the integer $n = 12$ in MID.

Like the complete symmetry between all divisors within the MID and the origin $(0,0)$, there is also total symmetry between all divisors of the integer 12 and the center shifted to $(12,0)$. The symmetry of its divisors occurs along the lines $x = 12$, $x = y + 12$, and $x = -y + 12$.

This remarkable symmetry pattern extends to every integer within the MID, reflecting the fundamental order and balance inherent in the distribution of divisors. Understanding this symmetry propagation is fundamental in comprehending the idea behind the production of prime numbers as mentioned in [“An idea for a new class of some numbers”](#).

5 Hyperbolas on the Center of XY-plane

As we delve into the realm of the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID), let us remember that any integer within the FMT (Full Multiplication Table) framework[14] can be represented within a two-dimensional hyperbolic lattice grid. Now, envision superimposing the FMT lattice onto the MID's lattice, both residing within the same plane.

To illustrate this concept, consider the hyperbola $xy = \pm 12$ represented in maroon in Figure 5. Observe how this hyperbola intersects the MID lattice at specific points. This intersection corresponds to the divisors 6 at (6,2) and 1 at (12,1) of 12 within the MID.

Figure 5. The $xy = \pm 12$ hyperbolas in MID.

The maroon hyperbolas, represented by the equation $x * y = n$, for $n > 0$, possess the following characteristics:

- transverse axis equation: $x = y$
- conjugate axis equation: $x = -y$
- center point at: $(0,0)$
- vertices point at: $(\sqrt{n}, \sqrt{n})$ and $(-\sqrt{n}, -\sqrt{n})$
- circle: $x^2 + y^2 = 2n$
- vertical asymptote equation: $x = 0$
- horizontal asymptote equation: $y = 0$

So, we can express any integer in the form of:

$$xy = n = d_1 d_2$$

This formula encapsulates the essence of FMT, where any integer n can be expressed in the form of $xy = n = d_1 * d_2$. This implies that as d_1 increases, d_2 correspondingly decreases, and vice versa.

The relationship between d_1 and d_2 within FMT is mirrored in the hyperbolic nature of the hyperbolas.

This means that for each integer n constant, if d_1 increases, then d_2 decreases, and vice versa.

- if d_1 increases linearly, then d_2 decreases hyperbolically.
- if d_1 decreases linearly, then d_2 increases hyperbolically.
- if d_2 increases linearly, then d_1 decreases hyperbolically.
- if d_2 decreases linearly, then d_1 increases hyperbolically.

5.1 Hyperbolas for Each Integer: A Unique Signature

Having established the linear equations for divisor lines associated with each integer, the next step is to determine the corresponding hyperbolic equations for the divisors of each integer within the MID.

The same FMT concept applies to the MID, but with distinct positions for each integer. The challenge lies in translocating the center of the FMT hyperbola from $(0,0)$ to a suitable location within the MID to encompass each integer.

5.2 Translocating Hyperbolas Centers

As a first approach, consider translocating the FMT hyperbolas along the $+45^\circ$ diagonals. The discussion regarding the conjugated hyperbolas along the -45° diagonals will be left for the reader to explore.

In the FMT hyperbolas, the center is located at $(0,0)$, and the asymptotes are vertical at $x = 0$ and horizontal at $y = 0$. However, within the MID, the vertical asymptotes must align with $x = n = d_1 * d_2$.

The $+45^\circ$ diagonal has its center or origin at $(n, 0)$. For every n , the first divisor encountered is divisor 1. All other divisors lie along the diagonal line. Therefore, the hyperbola must translocate one step along the positive direction of the Y-axis.

The horizontal asymptote remains at $y = 1$, ensuring the hyperbola's hyperbolic nature.

The original center $(0,0)$ of the FMT hyperbola shifts to a new center within the MID lattice: $(x, y) = (n, 1) = (d_1 * d_2, 1)$.

The figure below illustrates in pink this shift for integer $n = 12$.

Figure 6. The shifted center of the MID hyperbola for integer $n = 12$ over the horizontal $y = 1$.

Mathematically, the center in FMT is at $(0,0)$:

$$y = \frac{n}{x} = \frac{d_1 d_2}{x}$$

When translocated to the new center $(n, 1) = (d_1 d_2, 1)$, the new equation emerges:

$$y = \frac{n}{x - n} + 1 = \frac{d_1 d_2}{x - d_1 d_2} + 1$$

Alternatively, the equation can be expressed as:

$$y = \frac{n}{x - n} + 1$$

$$y(x - n) = n + (x - n)$$

$$xy - ny = x$$

$$xy = ny + x$$

$$1 = \frac{n}{x} + \frac{1}{y} = \frac{d_1 d_2}{x} + \frac{1}{y}$$

From $xy = n = d_1 d_2$, we can derive another approach by moving n positions in the X-axis direction and 1 position in the Y-axis direction. Let us define $x'y' = n = d_1 d_2$, where:

$$x' = (x - n)$$

$$y' = (y - 1)$$

Then,

$$x'y' = (x - n)(y - 1) = n$$

$$xy - x - ny + n = n$$

$$xy - x - ny = 0$$

$$xy = x + ny$$

$$1 = \frac{n}{x} + \frac{1}{y} = \frac{d_1 d_2}{x} + \frac{1}{y}$$

Figure 7. Hyperbola $xy = x + 12y$ (pink) covering all divisors of integer 12 over the diagonal $x = y + 12$.

The pink hyperbolas, represented by the equation $xy = x + ny$, for $n > 0$, possess the following characteristics:

- transverse axis equation: $x = y + n$
- conjugate axis equation: $x = -y + n$
- center point at: $(n, 1)$
- vertices point at: $(n + \sqrt{n}, 1 + \sqrt{n})$ and $(n - \sqrt{n}, 1 - \sqrt{n})$
- circle: $(x - n)^2 + (y - 1)^2 = 2n$
- vertical asymptote equation: $x = n$
- horizontal asymptote equation: $y = 1$

The same divisor's hyperbola $xy=n$ covers in the FMT, now the $xy = x + ny$ hyperbola covers in the MID.

Figure 8. Shift of the divisors from integer 12 in hyperbola $xy = 12$ to the divisors in hyperbola $xy = x + 12y$. (File: Example with Number 12.ggb)

All vectors of translocation have a slope of $1:12$.

For each divisor of $n = 12$ covered by the hyperbola $xy = x + 12y$, there is a corresponding one on the vertical line $x = 12$. Similarly, for every divisor covered by the vertical line $x = 12$, there is a corresponding one on the $\pm 45^\circ$ diagonals $x = \pm y + 12$.

This observation highlights an inherent connection between the hyperbolas and the distribution of divisors within the MID. The hyperbolas effectively map the divisors onto their respective positions, revealing the underlying order and symmetry inherent in the MID structure.

The one-unit translocation of the hyperbolas's center along the Y-axis introduces an intrinsic offset of one unit between the transverse and conjugate axes of the hyperbolas $xy = x + ny$ and the divisors' diagonals $x = \pm y + n$. This offset is a consequence of the shift and plays a crucial role in ensuring that the hyperbolas accurately represent the distribution of divisors within the MID.

6 The Oblong Parabolic Trajectory of the Vertices

The two vertices of the $xy = x + ny$ hyperbola is represented by coordinates at $(n + \sqrt{n}, 1 + \sqrt{n})$ and $(n - \sqrt{n}, 1 - \sqrt{n})$. These vertices vary as a quadratic function in the form of $\sqrt{n}$. Because they relate to the origin (0,0) as reference, the three points collectively define an oblong parabola that intersects these vertices. Specifically, the parabolic path traced by the vertices follows the equation $x = y^2 - y$, which corresponds to an oblong number parabola.

Figure 9. Illustrates the oblong parabolic trajectory of the vertices, depicted by the dashed pink parabola.

7 Key Definitions

Let us make the definitions:

- **Yuri-Boris (YB) Diagonals:** The Yuri-Boris diagonals, also known as YB diagonals in MID, are the lines discovered by Yuri Matiyasevich and Boris Stechkin in their

work "A Visual Sieve for Prime Numbers." [24] These diagonals are duals and symmetric concerning the X-axis.

- **Parabola Sieve of Primes (PSP):** The "A Visual Sieve for Prime Numbers" [24] is also referred to as the Parabola Sieve of Primes (PSP).
- **PSP Parabola in MID:** is defined as the set of two parabolas: $x = \pm y^2$.
- **HPSP Point:** in this context refers to any point on the PSP parabola intersecting a hyperbola.
- **HPSP Diagonal:** is defined as a line formed by any two distinct HPSP points on the PSP parabola. To ensure a continuous solution for the hyperbola's line, we consider the asymptotes of the hyperbolas as part of the hyperbola. This definition includes vertical and horizontal lines as HPSP diagonals.
- **Triangular Sieve of Primes (TSP) Diagonals [10]:** TSP diagonals are any HPSP diagonals that intersect the X-axis and Y-axis with integer coordinates.

Relationships between diagonals:

- All TSP diagonals intersect the XY axes at points with integer coordinates.
- All TSP diagonals are HPSP diagonals, but the inverse is not always valid.
- TSP diagonals include any HPSP diagonals intersecting the X-axis and Y-axis with integer coordinates.
- Every YB diagonal utilizes only pairs of square points on the PSP parabola to create a diagonal.
- All YB diagonals are also HPSP diagonals, but the reverse is not true.
- A TSP diagonal may or may not be a YB diagonal, and vice versa.

These diagonals are the CGs (Composite Generators) that bound all non-CG quadratic sequences in [C002209 The Oblong Parabolic Sieve of Primes](#) also link [PS\[x+2,x,x\]](#), and in [C002210 The square parabolic sieve of primes](#) also link [PS\[x+1,x,x+1\]](#).

8 Diagonals of Hyperbolas over the PSP Parabola

Let us determine the points where the pink hyperbola, represented by $xy = x + ny$, intersects the PSP parabola $x = y^2$. By substituting $x = y^2$ into the hyperbola equation:

$$\begin{aligned} xy &= x + ny \\ y^3 &= y^2 + ny \\ y^3 - y^2 - ny &= 0 \\ y(y^2 - y - n) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Excluding the trivial solution at the X-axis where $y = 0$:

$$y^2 - y - n = 0$$

Or,

$$y^2 - y - d_1 d_2 = 0$$

$$y_{1,2} = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{1 + 4d_1d_2}}{2}$$

This implies that when $4d_1d_2$ is a square-1 number (or $1 + 4d_1d_2 = \text{square}$), the hyperbola $xy = x + ny$ intersects the parabola at two Cartesian HPSP points with integer coordinates. These points create an HPSP diagonal. This occurs when:

$$4d_1d_2 = 4n = q^2 - 1 = (q - 1)(q + 1) = r(r \pm 2) = 2s(2s \pm 2) = 4s(s \pm 1) = 4(s^2 \pm s) \\ = 4 * \text{Oblong}$$

Oblong numbers are in the form of $n = d_{c1}d_{c2}$ for $d_{c2} - d_{c1} = b_d = 1$. Thus,

$$y_{1,2} = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{1 + 4d_{c1}(d_{c1} + 1)}}{2} = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{4d_{c1}^2 + 4d_{c1} + 1}}{2} = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{(2d_{c1} + 1)^2}}{2} \\ = \frac{1 \pm (2d_{c1} + 1)}{2}$$

$$y_1 = d_{c1} + 1 \text{ and } x_1 = (d_{c1} + 1)^2 = d_{c1}^2 + 2d_{c1} + 1$$

$$y_2 = -d_{c1} \text{ and } x_2 = d_{c1}^2$$

These coordinates generate the YB diagonals for all oblong numbers.

Conclusion: For every $n = d_1d_2$ where $b_d = d_2 - d_1 = 1$ oblong number, the pink hyperbola $xy = x + d_1d_2y$ intersects the PSP parabola $x = y^2$ at two Cartesian HPSP points with integer coordinates. These HPSP diagonals are YB diagonals.

9 Not Only Oblong Numbers

What exactly causes the intersections of the hyperbola with the PSP parabola to yield YB diagonals exclusively for oblong numbers? How can we generate YB diagonals for all other integers?

Let us trace our steps backward:

We identified two Cartesian HPSP points with integer coordinates because the discriminant $\Delta = 1 + 4n$ forms a perfect square, q^2 . Our findings exclusively involved oblong numbers since we enforced $4n = q^2 - 1$, demonstrating that this condition only holds true for oblong numbers.

But where did the number 1 in the discriminant $\Delta = 1 + 4n$ originate?

It stems from the coefficient $b = -1$ in the quadratic equation $y^2 - y - n = 0$.

What happens if we change the coefficient $b = -1$ to any other integer $b = -b_d$? We obtain the quadratic equation: $y^2 - b_dy - n = 0$. Consequently, the discriminant becomes $\Delta = (-b_d)^2 + 4n = b_d^2 + 4n$. When $\Delta = b_d^2 + 4n$ forms perfect squares, the discriminant yields integer roots.

As previously observed, we can uniquely express every integer as the product of its central pair of complementary divisors. The absolute difference between these divisors determines the type or class of quadratic number. A difference of $b_d = 1$ between the divisors signifies oblong numbers, $b_d = 0$ signifies square numbers, a difference of $b_d = 2$ signifies (squares minus 1) numbers, and so forth.

Because $n = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$ and $b_d = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= (d_{c2} - d_{c1})^2 + 4d_{c1}d_{c2} \\ \Delta &= d_{c2}^2 + d_{c1}^2 - 2d_{c1}d_{c2} + 4d_{c1}d_{c2} \\ \Delta &= d_{c2}^2 + d_{c1}^2 + 2d_{c1}d_{c2}\end{aligned}$$

And..., deliciously:

$$\Delta = (d_{c2} + d_{c1})^2$$

For any integer number $n = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$ and $b_d = d_{c2} - d_{c1}$, the discriminant will invariably be a perfect square.

10 The Hyperbolas Generating all YB Diagonals

Now, let us derive the equation of the hyperbola that generates YB diagonals.

It is crucial to note that we can exclusively create YB diagonals through hyperbolas that intersect the PSP parabola and yield the quadratic equation in the form of:

$$y^2 - (d_2 - d_1)y - d_1d_2 = 0$$

So, working backward:

$$y(y^2 - (d_2 - d_1)y - d_1d_2) = 0$$

$$y^3 - (d_2 - d_1)y^2 - d_1d_2y = 0$$

$$y^3 = (d_2 - d_1)y^2 + d_1d_2y$$

Let us substitute y^2 for x , and the equation of the hyperbola becomes:

$$xy = (d_2 - d_1)x + d_1d_2y$$

$$xy = (\text{difference})x + (\text{product})y$$

11 The General Equation of MID Hyperbolas and Their Parameters

Based on these findings, we will establish the generalized equation of hyperbolas in MID as follows:

Alternatively,

$$xy = bx + cy$$

$$1 = \frac{b}{y} + \frac{c}{x}$$

Please refer to the figure below for the adopted nomenclature in this study.

Figure 10. C000705 Example for $c = n = 10$ and $b = bd = 3$. In this instance, the HPSP diagonal represents a YB diagonal because $n = 10 = 2 * 5$ and $5 - 2 = 3 = b_d$.

We denote all points using capital letters accompanied by a sequential numerical index. Additionally, line segments, lengths, and distances are denoted in capital letters accompanied by a subscript alphabetical index.

11.1 Asymptotes of Hyperbolas in MID

Vertical Asymptote:

If $x = c$:

$$xy = bx + cy$$

$$cy = bc + cy$$

$$y = b + y$$

This remains undefined for any value of y . Therefore, the vertical line $x = c$ represents an asymptote for the hyperbola.

Horizontal Asymptote:

If $y = b$:

$$xy = bx + cy$$

$$bx = bx + cb$$

$$x = x + c$$

This remains undefined for any value of x . Hence, the horizontal line $y = b$ represents an asymptote for the hyperbola.

Understanding Coefficients:

The coefficient b shifts the hyperbola center along the Y-axis direction, whereas the coefficient c shifts the hyperbola center along the X-axis direction.

Conclusion:

Equation of Vertical Asymptote: $x = c$ (where c denotes the position along the X-axis).

Equation of Horizontal Asymptote: $y = b$ (where b signifies the height along the Y-axis).

11.2 Center Point of the Hyperbola

The center point is the intersection point of the two asymptotes.

Therefore, in this context:

- n , or x , or c denotes the position of the center along the X-axis coordinate.
- b , or b_d signifies the height along the Y-axis coordinate.

Conclusion:

$$\text{Center Point: } C = (x_c, y_c) = (c, b)$$

Here:

c represents the position of the hyperbola center along the X-axis.

b represents the height of the hyperbola center along the Y-axis.

11.3 Transverse and Conjugate Axes of the Hyperbola

Given that the asymptotes are orthogonal and parallel to the X and Y axes, the transverse axis corresponds to the $+45^\circ$ diagonal, and the conjugate axis corresponds to the -45° diagonal. Both axes intersect at the hyperbola center point $(x_c, y_c) = (c, b)$.

The equation of the transverse axis takes the form $x = m_t y + k_t$. Since the transverse axis aligns with the $+45^\circ$ diagonal, $m_t = 1$. Therefore, the transverse axis equation becomes $x = y + k_t$. To intersect the center at $(x_c, y_c) = (c, b)$, it follows that $c = b + k_t$, leading to $k_t = c - b$.

Similarly, the equation of the conjugate axis is in the form $x = m_c y + k_c$. As the conjugate axis aligns with the -45° diagonal, $m_c = -1$. Consequently, the conjugate axis equation becomes $x = -y + k_c$. To intersect the center at $(x_c, y_c) = (c, b)$, we have $c = -b + k_c$, resulting in $k_c = c + b$.

Conclusion:

Transverse Axis Equation: $x = y + c - b$ (diagonal $+45^\circ$).

Conjugate Axis Equation: $x = -y + c + b$ (diagonal -45°).

11.4 Vertices of the Hyperbola

The vertices denote the points where the transverse axis intersects the hyperbola $xy = bx + cy$. By substituting $x = y + c - b$ into the hyperbola equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 xy &= bx + cy \\
 (y + c - b)y &= b(y + c - b) + cy \\
 y^2 + cy - by &= by + bc - b^2 + cy \\
 y^2 - 2by + b^2 - bc &= 0 \\
 y_{1,2} &= \frac{2b \pm \sqrt{4b^2 - 4b^2 + 4bc}}{2} = b \pm \sqrt{bc} \\
 x_{1,2} &= y_{1,2} + c - b \\
 x_{1,2} &= c \pm \sqrt{bc}
 \end{aligned}$$

Conclusion:

Vertices Point 1: $V1 = (x_{V1}, y_{V1}) = (c + \sqrt{bc}, b + \sqrt{bc})$.

Vertices Point 2: $V2 = (x_{V2}, y_{V2}) = (c - \sqrt{bc}, b - \sqrt{bc})$.

11.5 Co-Vertices of the Hyperbola

The co-vertices represent the points along the conjugate axis of the hyperbola $xy = bx + cy$. As the transverse and conjugate axes are perpendicular to each other, the co-vertices are equidistant from the center and maintain the same distance from the vertices.

Conclusion:

Co-Vertices Point 1: $CV1 = (x_{CV1}, y_{CV1}) = (x_{V2}, y_{V1}) = (c - \sqrt{bc}, b + \sqrt{bc})$.

Co-Vertices Point 2: $CV2 = (x_{CV2}, y_{CV2}) = (x_{V1}, y_{V2}) = (c + \sqrt{bc}, b - \sqrt{bc})$.

11.6 Transverse and Conjugate Lengths of the Hyperbola

The transverse length represents the distance between the center point $(x_c, y_c) = (c, b)$ and any vertex point, such as $(x_{V1}, y_{V1}) = (c + \sqrt{bc}, b + \sqrt{bc})$ or $(x_{V2}, y_{V2}) = (c - \sqrt{bc}, b - \sqrt{bc})$. Conversely, the conjugate length signifies the distance between the center point $(x_c, y_c) = (c, b)$

and any co-vertex point, such as $(x_{V2}, y_{V1}) = (c - \sqrt{bc}, b + \sqrt{bc})$ or $(x_{V1}, y_{V2}) = (c + \sqrt{bc}, b - \sqrt{bc})$.

In both cases, the transverse length T_L is identical to the conjugate length C_L . This equality emerges due to the orthogonality between the two asymptotes of the hyperbola.

$$\text{radius} = R = \sqrt{(x_v - x_c)^2 + (y_v - y_c)^2} = \sqrt{(c \pm \sqrt{bc} - c)^2 + (b \pm \sqrt{bc} - b)^2} = \sqrt{bc + bc}$$

Conclusion:

Transverse Length: $T_L = \sqrt{2bc}$.

Conjugate Length: $C_L = \sqrt{2bc}$.

11.7 The Circle of Vertices of the Hyperbola

Since the two vertices and the two co-vertices are equidistant from the center point of the hyperbola, then we can draw a circle that reflects this property.

Conclusion:

The equation of the circle inscribed in the hyperbole $xy = bx + cy$ is:

$$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = T_L^2 = C_L^2 = 2bc$$

11.8 The Focal Length, Focal Circle, Foci Points, and Foci Distance of the Hyperbola

Let us denote the focal length (F_L) as the distance from a focal point to the center, constituting half the foci distance (F_D):

$$\begin{aligned} F_L^2 &= T_L^2 + C_L^2 \\ F_L^2 &= 2bc + 2bc \\ F_L &= \sqrt{4bc} = 2\sqrt{bc} \\ F_D &= 2F_L \\ F_D &= 4\sqrt{bc} \end{aligned}$$

Conclusion:

Focal Length = $F_L = \frac{F_D}{2} = 2\sqrt{bc}$.

Foci Distance = $F_D = 2F_L = 4\sqrt{bc}$.

Focus Point 1: $F1 = (x_{F1}, y_{F1}) = (c + \sqrt{2bc}, b + \sqrt{2bc})$.

Focus Point 2: $F2 = (x_{F2}, y_{F2}) = (c - \sqrt{2bc}, b - \sqrt{2bc})$.

Focal Circle: $(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = F_L^2 = 4bc$.

11.9 The Eccentricity of the Hyperbola

$$\text{Eccentricity: } e = \frac{F_L}{T_L} = \frac{2\sqrt{bc}}{\sqrt{2bc}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{2}} = \sqrt{2}.$$

11.10 The HPSP points

The general equation of hyperbolas is given by $xy = bx + cy$. When this hyperbola intersects the PSP parabola at $x = y^2$, the following calculations arise:

$$\begin{aligned}y^3 - by^2 - cy &= 0 \\y(y^2 - by - c) &= 0\end{aligned}$$

The trivial solution exists when $y = 0$ and $x = 0$, indicating that the first HPSP point is the origin (0,0) where the X-axis and Y-axis intersect the PSP parabola. For hyperbolas in the form of $xy = constant$, including $xy = bx + cy$, this intersection occurs with an offset along the X and Y axes. However, if we consider the conjugate hyperbola, the offset only exists in the Y-axis translocation, as the X-axis, behaving as an asymptote, remains stationary. This concept could be further explored in a separate study.

The non-trivial solution is determined by the roots:

$$y_{HPSP1,2} = \frac{b \pm \sqrt{(-b)^2 + 4c}}{2}$$

Because the discriminant is always positive, two distinct HPSP points are always present where the hyperbola intersects the PSP parabola.

$$\begin{aligned}y_{HP1} &= \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \\x_{HP1} = y_{HP1}^2 &= \left(\frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{b^2 + b^2 + 4c + 2b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{4} = \frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \\y_{HP2} &= \frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \\x_{HP2} = y_{HP2}^2 &= \left(\frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{b^2 + b^2 + 4c - 2b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{4} = \frac{b^2 + 2c - b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}\end{aligned}$$

Conclusion:

$$HPSP \text{ point } 1 = HP1 = (x_{HP1}, y_{HP1}) = \left(\frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}, \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}\right)$$

$$HPSP \text{ point } 2 = HP2 = (x_{HP2}, y_{HP2}) = \left(\frac{b^2 + 2c - b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}, \frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}\right)$$

These two distinct HPSP points form an HPSP diagonal. They represent a YB diagonal when HP1 and HP2 have integer coordinates, occurring when $b^2 + 4c$ is a square number.

11.11 The HPSP diagonals

The HPSP diagonal follows the form $y = mx + h$, where:

$$m = \frac{y_{HP1} - y_{HP2}}{x_{HP1} - x_{HP2}} = \frac{\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}} = \frac{1}{b}$$

Thus, the equation becomes:

$$y = \frac{x}{b} + h$$

To find h :

$$y_{HP1} = \frac{x_{HP1}}{b} + h$$

$$\frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} = \frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2b} + h$$

$$\frac{b^2 + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} = \frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} + bh$$

$$h = -\frac{c}{b}$$

The line equation reads:

$$y = \frac{x}{b} - \frac{c}{b}$$

Now, expressing the HPSP diagonal equation as a function of y :

$$x = by + bh$$

$$x = by + k$$

Where:

$$x_1 = by_1 + k$$

$$\frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} = b \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} + k$$

$$k = \frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} - \frac{b^2 + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}$$

$$k = c$$

The HPSP diagonals equation is:

Conclusion:

The HPSP diagonals equation becomes:

$$\text{HPSP diagonal} = y = \frac{x}{b} - \frac{c}{b}$$

$$\text{HPSP diagonal} = x = by + c$$

For positive values of b , the larger the value of b , the more inclined the ascending HPSP diagonal becomes.

11.12 The HPSP Center Point

The HPSP center point, also known as the HPSP diagonal center point, is the sole point on the HPSP diagonal equidistant from the two HPSP points. To find this point:

$$\text{HPSP point 1} = HP1 = (x_{HP}, y_{HP}) = \left(\frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}, \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \right)$$

$$HPSP \text{ point } 2 = HP2 = (x_{HP2}, y_{HP2}) = \left(\frac{b^2 + 2c - b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}, \frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \right)$$

The HPSP center point (HPC) can be calculated as:

$$HPSP \text{ center point} = (x_c, y_c) = \left(\frac{x_{HP1} + x_{HP2}}{2}, \frac{y_{HP1} + y_{HP2}}{2} \right)$$

$$\frac{x_{HP1} + x_{HP2}}{2} = \frac{\frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} + \frac{b^2 + 2c - b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}}{2} = \frac{b^2 + 2c}{2}$$

$$\frac{y_{HP1} + y_{HP2}}{2} = \frac{\frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} + \frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}}{2} = \frac{b}{2}$$

Conclusion:

$$HPSP \text{ center point} = HPC = (x_{HPC}, y_{HPC}) = \left(\frac{b^2 + 2c}{2}, \frac{b}{2} \right)$$

11.13 The HPSP Length, HPSP Circle, and HPSP Distance

The HPSP length (HP_L) is the distance between each HPSP point ($HP1$ and $HP2$) and the HPSP center point (HPC):

$$HPSP \text{ point } 1 = HP1 = (x_{HP1}, y_{HP1}) = \left(\frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}, \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \right)$$

$$HPSP \text{ center point} = HPC = (x_{HPC}, y_{HPC}) = \left(\frac{b^2 + 2c}{2}, \frac{b}{2} \right)$$

So,

$$HP_L = \sqrt{\left(\frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} - \frac{b^2 + 2c}{2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} - \frac{b}{2} \right)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{\left(\frac{b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \right)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{b^2(b^2 + 4c)}{4} + \frac{(b^2 + 4c)}{4}}$$

$$= \frac{\sqrt{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4c)}}{2}$$

$$HP_L = \frac{\sqrt{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4c)}}{2}$$

The HPSP circle equation is derived from the circle centered at the HPSP center point (HPC) with radius HP_L :

$$(x - x_{HPC})^2 + (y - y_{HPC})^2 = HP_L^2$$

$$\left(x - \frac{b^2 + 2c}{2} \right)^2 + \left(y - \frac{b}{2} \right)^2 = \frac{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4c)}{4}$$

The HPSP distance (HP_D) is twice the HPSP length and is equivalent to the diameter of the HPSP circle:

$$HP_D = 2HP_L = \sqrt{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4c)}$$

Conclusion:

$$\text{HPSP length: } HP_L = \frac{HP_D}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{(b^2+1)(b^2+4c)}}{2}$$

$$\text{HPSP circle: } \left(x - \frac{b^2+2c}{2}\right)^2 + \left(y - \frac{b}{2}\right)^2 = HP_L^2 = \frac{(b^2+1)(b^2+4c)}{4}$$

$$\text{HPSP distance: } HP_D = 2HP_L = \sqrt{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4c)}$$

12 Summary:

The table below provides a detailed summary of equations and parameters related to hyperbolas based on real numbers b and c . Each section outlines distinct aspects of the hyperbola, including equations for asymptotes, vertices, focal points, HPSP points, diagonals, center points, lengths, circles, distances, and more.

Description	Notation	Equation
Hyperbola	equation	$xy = bx + cy$ or $1 = \frac{b}{y} + \frac{c}{x}$
Divisors' Vertical	equation	$x = c$
Divisors' Diag. Asc.	equation	$x = y + c$
Divisors' Diag. Desc.	equation	$x - y + c$
Vertical Asymptote	equation $x = \text{constant}$	$x = c$
Horizontal Asymptote	equation $y = \text{constant}$	$y = b$
Center Point	$C = (x_C, y_C)$	(c, b)
Transverse Axis	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = y + c - b$
Conjugate Axis	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = -y + c + b$
Vertices Point 1	$V1 = (x_{V1}, y_{V1})$	$(c + \sqrt{bc}, b + \sqrt{bc})$
Vertices Point 2	$V2 = (x_{V2}, y_{V2})$	$(c - \sqrt{bc}, b - \sqrt{bc})$
Co-Vertices Point 1	$CV1 = (x_{CV1}, y_{CV1}) = (x_{V2}, y_{V1})$	$(c - \sqrt{bc}, b + \sqrt{bc})$
Co-Vertices Point 2	$CV2 = (x_{CV2}, y_{CV2}) = (x_{V1}, y_{V2})$	$(c + \sqrt{bc}, b - \sqrt{bc})$
Transverse Length	T_L	$\sqrt{2bc}$
Conjugate Length	C_L	$\sqrt{2bc}$
Circle of Vertices	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = TL^2$	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = 2bc$
Focal Distance	$F_D = 2F_L$	$4\sqrt{bc}$
Focal Length	$F_L = \frac{F_D}{2}$	$2\sqrt{bc}$
Focus Point 1	$F1 = (x_{F1}, y_{F1})$	$(c + \sqrt{2bc}, b + \sqrt{2bc})$
Focus Point 2	$F2 = (x_{F2}, y_{F2})$	$(c - \sqrt{2bc}, b - \sqrt{2bc})$
Circle of Foci	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = D_F^2$	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = 4bc$

Eccentricity	$e = \frac{F_L}{T_L}$	$\sqrt{2}$
HPSP Point 1	$HP1 = (x_{HP1}, y_{HP1})$	$\left(\frac{b^2 + 2c + b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}, \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \right)$
HPSP Point 2	$HP2 = (x_{HP2}, y_{HP2})$	$\left(\frac{b^2 + 2c - b\sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2}, \frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 + 4c}}{2} \right)$
HPSP Diagonal X[x]	equation $y = X[x]$	$y = \frac{x}{b} - \frac{c}{b}$
HPSP Diagonal Y[y]	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = by + c$
HPSP Center Point	$HPC = (x_{HPC}, y_{HPC})$	$\left(\frac{b^2 + 2c}{2}, \frac{b}{2} \right)$
HPSP Length	$HP_L = \frac{HP_D}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4c)}}{2}$
HPSP Circle	$(x - x_{HPC})^2 + (y - y_{HPC})^2 = HP_L^2$	$\left(x - \frac{b^2 + 2c}{2} \right)^2 + \left(y - \frac{b}{2} \right)^2 = \frac{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4c)}{4}$
HPSP Distance	$HP_D = 2HP_L$	$\sqrt{(b^2 + 1)(b^2 + 4c)}$

12.1 Refined Example:

Demonstration when the HPSP diagonal transforms into a YB diagonal by intersecting the YB parabola precisely at points characterized by integer coordinates:

Figure 11. C000705 The example above for $c = n = 10$ and $b = b_d = 3$.

Figure 12. C000705 The example above for $c = n = 10$ and $b = b_d = 2$. Now, the HPSP diagonal is a TSP diagonal. This is because $\frac{-n}{b_d} = -5$ which is the Y coordinate of HPSP diagonal at $x = 0$.

12.2 Table for Integer Parameters

The table below provides a detailed summary of equations and parameters related to hyperbolas based on real numbers $b = b_d$ and $c = n$.

Description	Notation	Equation
Hyperbola	<i>equation</i>	$xy = b_d x + ny$ or $1 = \frac{b_d}{y} + \frac{n}{x}$

Divisors' Vertical	equation	$x = n$
Divisors' Diag. Asc.	equation	$x = y + n$
Divisors' Diag. Desc.	equation	$x - y + n$
Vertical Asymptote	equation $x = \text{constant}$	$x = n$
Horizontal Asymptote	equation $y = \text{constant}$	$y = b_d$
Center Point	$C = (x_C, y_C)$	(n, b_d)
Transverse Axis	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = y + n - b_d$
Conjugate Axis	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = -y + n + b_d$
Vertices Point 1	$V1 = (x_{V1}, y_{V1})$	$(n + \sqrt{b_d n}, b_d + \sqrt{b_d n})$
Vertices Point 2	$V2 = (x_{V2}, y_{V2})$	$(n - \sqrt{b_d n}, b_d - \sqrt{b_d n})$
Co-Vertices Point 1	$CV1 = (x_{CV1}, y_{CV1}) = (x_{V2}, y_{V1})$	$(n - \sqrt{b_d n}, b_d + \sqrt{b_d n})$
Co-Vertices Point 2	$CV2 = (x_{CV2}, y_{CV2}) = (x_{V1}, y_{V2})$	$(n + \sqrt{b_d n}, b_d - \sqrt{b_d n})$
Transverse Length	T_L	$\sqrt{2b_d n}$
Conjugate Length	C_L	$\sqrt{2b_d n}$
Circle of Vertices	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = T_L^2$	$(x - n)^2 + (y - b_d)^2 = 2b_d n$
Focal Distance	$F_D = 2F_L$	$4\sqrt{b_d n}$
Focal Length	$F_L = \frac{F_D}{2}$	$2\sqrt{b_d n}$
Focus Point 1	$F1 = (x_{F1}, y_{F1})$	$(n + \sqrt{2b_d n}, b_d + \sqrt{2b_d n})$
Focus Point 2	$F2 = (x_{F2}, y_{F2})$	$(n - \sqrt{2b_d n}, b_d - \sqrt{2b_d n})$
Circle of Foci	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = D_F^2$	$(x - n)^2 + (y - b_d)^2 = 4b_d n$
Eccentricity	$e = \frac{F_L}{T_L}$	$\sqrt{2}$
HPSP Point 1	$HP1 = (x_{HP1}, y_{HP1})$	$\left(\frac{b_d^2 + 2n + b_d \sqrt{b_d^2 + 4n}}{2}, \frac{b_d + \sqrt{b_d^2 + 4n}}{2} \right)$
HPSP Point 2	$HP2 = (x_{HP2}, y_{HP2})$	$\left(\frac{b_d^2 + 2n - b_d \sqrt{b_d^2 + 4n}}{2}, \frac{b_d - \sqrt{b_d^2 + 4n}}{2} \right)$
HPSP Diagonal X[x]	equation $y = X[x]$	$y = \frac{x}{b_d} - \frac{n}{b_d}$
HPSP Diagonal Y[y]	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = b_d y + n$
HPSP Center Point	$HPC = (x_{HPC}, y_{HPC})$	$\left(\frac{b_d^2 + 2n}{2}, \frac{b_d}{2} \right)$
HPSP Length	$HP_L = \frac{HP_D}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{(b_d^2 + 1)(b_d^2 + 4n)}}{2}$
HPSP Circle	$(x - x_{HPC})^2 + (y - y_{HPC})^2 = HP_L^2$	$\left(x - \frac{b_d^2 + 2n}{2} \right)^2 + \left(y - \frac{b_d}{2} \right)^2 = \frac{(b_d^2 + 1)(b_d^2 + 4n)}{4}$
HPSP Distance	$HP_D = 2HP_L$	$\sqrt{(b_d^2 + 1)(b_d^2 + 4n)}$

Figure 13. C000705 Summary table with $b = b_d$ and $c = n$ Integer numbers.

13 The YB Diagonals

The occurrence of YB diagonals is contingent upon $b = b_d = d_2 - d_1$ and $c = n = d_1d_2$.

13.1 Vertices and Co-Vertices Points

Vertices and co-vertices points assume integer coordinates when $b_d n = \text{square}$:

$$\sqrt{b_d n} = \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2} = \sqrt{d_1d_2^2 - d_1^2d_2}$$

13.2 The HPSP Points 1 and 2

$$\begin{aligned} x_{HP1} &= \frac{b_d^2 + 2n + b_d\sqrt{b_d^2 + 4n}}{2} = \frac{(d_2 - d_1)^2 + 2d_1d_2 + (d_2 - d_1)\sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)^2 + 4d_1d_2}}{2} \\ &= \frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2 - 2d_1d_2 + 2d_1d_2 + (d_2 - d_1)\sqrt{d_2^2 + d_1^2 - 2d_1d_2 + 4d_1d_2}}{2} \\ &= \frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2 + (d_2 - d_1)\sqrt{d_2^2 + d_1^2 + 2d_1d_2}}{2} = \frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2 + (d_2 - d_1)\sqrt{(d_2 + d_1)^2}}{2} \\ &= \frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2 + (d_2 - d_1)(d_2 + d_1)}{2} = \frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2 + d_2^2 - d_1^2}{2} = d_2^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$y_{HP1} = \frac{b_d + \sqrt{b_d^2 + 4n}}{2} = \frac{d_2 - d_1 + d_2 + d_1}{2} = d_2$$

$$x_{HP2} = \frac{b_d^2 + 2n - b_d\sqrt{b_d^2 + 4n}}{2} = \frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2 - (d_2 - d_1)(d_2 + d_1)}{2} = \frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2 - d_2^2 + d_1^2}{2} = d_1^2$$

$$y_{HP2} = \frac{b_d - \sqrt{b_d^2 + 4n}}{2} = \frac{d_2 - d_1 - d_2 - d_1}{2} = -d_1$$

13.3 Summary Table for YB Diagonals

Description	Notation	Equation
Hyperbola	<i>equation</i>	$xy = (d_2 - d_1)x + d_1d_2y$ or $1 = \frac{d_2 - d_1}{y} + \frac{d_1d_2}{x}$
Divisors' Vertical	<i>equation</i>	$x = d_1d_2$
Divisors' Diag. Asc.	<i>equation</i>	$x = y + d_1d_2$
Divisors' Diag. Desc.	<i>equation</i>	$x - y + d_1d_2$
Vertical Asymptote	<i>equation</i> $x = \text{constant}$	$x = d_1d_2$
Horizontal Asymptote	<i>equation</i> $y = \text{constant}$	$y = d_2 - d_1$
Center Point	$C = (x_c, y_c)$	$(d_1d_2, d_2 - d_1)$
Transverse Axis	<i>equation</i> $x = Y[y]$	$x = y + d_1d_2 - (d_2 - d_1)$
Conjugate Axis	<i>equation</i> $x = Y[y]$	$x = -y + d_1d_2 + d_2 - d_1$
Vertices Point 1	$V1 = (x_{V1}, y_{V1})$	$(d_1d_2 + \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}, d_2 - d_1 + \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2})$
Vertices Point 2	$V2 = (x_{V2}, y_{V2})$	$(d_1d_2 - \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}, d_2 - d_1 - \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2})$

Co-Vertices Point 1	$CV1 = (x_{CV1}, y_{CV1})$	$(d_1d_2 - \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}, d_2 - d_1 + \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2})$
Co-Vertices Point 2	$CV2 = (x_{CV2}, y_{CV2})$	$(d_1d_2 + \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}, d_2 - d_1 - \sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2})$
Transverse Length	T_L	$\sqrt{2(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}$
Conjugate Length	C_L	$\sqrt{2(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}$
Circle of Vertices	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = T_L^2$	$(x - d_1d_2)^2 + (y - (d_2 - d_1))^2 = 2(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2$
Focal Distance	$F_D = 2F_L$	$4\sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}$
Focal Length	$F_L = \frac{F_D}{2}$	$2\sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}$
Focus Point 1	$F1 = (x_{F1}, y_{F1})$	$(d_1d_2 + \sqrt{2(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}, d_2 - d_1 + \sqrt{2(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2})$
Focus Point 2	$F2 = (x_{F2}, y_{F2})$	$(d_1d_2 - \sqrt{2(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2}, d_2 - d_1 - \sqrt{2(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2})$
Circle of Foci	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = D_F^2$	$(x - d_1d_2)^2 + (y - (d_2 - d_1))^2 = 4(d_2 - d_1)d_1d_2$
Eccentricity	$e = \frac{F_L}{T_L}$	$\sqrt{2}$
HPSP Point 1	$HP1 = (x_{HP1}, y_{HP1})$	(d_2^2, d_2)
HPSP Point 2	$HP2 = (x_{HP2}, y_{HP2})$	$(d_1^2, -d_1)$
HPSP Diagonal X[x]	equation $y = X[x]$	$y = \frac{x}{d_2 - d_1} - \frac{d_1d_2}{d_2 - d_1}$
HPSP Diagonal Y[y]	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = (d_2 - d_1)y + d_1d_2$
HPSP Center Point	$HPC = (x_{HPC}, y_{HPC})$	$(\frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2}{2}, \frac{d_2 - d_1}{2})$
HPSP Length	$HP_L = \frac{HP_D}{2}$	$\frac{(d_2 + d_1)\sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)^2 + 1}}{2}$
HPSP Circle	$(x - x_{HPC})^2 + (y - y_{HPC})^2 = HP_L^2$	$(x - \frac{d_2^2 + d_1^2}{2})^2 + (y - \frac{d_2 - d_1}{2})^2 = \frac{((d_2 - d_1)^2 + 1)(d_2 + d_1)^2}{4}$
HPSP Distance	$HP_D = 2HP_L$	$(d_2 + d_1)\sqrt{(d_2 - d_1)^2 + 1}$

Figure 14. C000705 Summary table with $b = b_d = d_2 - d_1$ and $c = n = d_1d_2$ Integer

13.4 The Trivial YB Diagonals

Every integer inherently possesses one trivial pair of complementary divisors, where $d_1 = \pm 1$ and $d_2 = n$. This inherent property allows us to establish a trivial YB diagonal by setting $b = b_d = d_2 - d_1 = n - 1$ and $c = n = d_1 * d_2 = n$.

Description	Notation	Equation
Hyperbola	equation	$xy = (n - 1)x + ny$ or $1 = \frac{(n - 1)}{y} + \frac{n}{x}$
Divisors' Vertical	equation	$x = n$
Divisors' Diag. Asc.	equation	$x = y + n$
Divisors' Diag. Desc.	equation	$x - y = n$

Vertical Asymptote	equation $x = \text{constant}$	$x = n$
Horizontal Asymptote	equation $y = \text{constant}$	$y = (n - 1)$
Center Point	$C = (x_C, y_C)$	$(n, n - 1)$
Transverse Axis	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = y + 1$
Conjugate Axis	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = -y + 2n - 1$
Vertices Point 1	$V1 = (x_{V1}, y_{V1})$	$(n + \sqrt{n(n-1)}, n - 1 + \sqrt{n(n-1)})$
Vertices Point 2	$V2 = (x_{V2}, y_{V2})$	$(n - \sqrt{n(n-1)}, n - 1 - \sqrt{n(n-1)})$
Co-Vertices Point 1	$CV1 = (x_{CV1}, y_{CV1})$	$(n - \sqrt{n(n-1)}, n - 1 + \sqrt{n(n-1)})$
Co-Vertices Point 2	$CV2 = (x_{CV2}, y_{CV2})$	$(n + \sqrt{n(n-1)}, n - 1 - \sqrt{n(n-1)})$
Transverse Length	T_L	$\sqrt{2n(n-1)}$
Conjugate Length	C_L	$\sqrt{2n(n-1)}$
Circle of Vertices	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = T_L^2$	$(x - n)^2 + (y - n - 1)^2 = 2n(n - 1)$
Focal Distance	$F_D = 2F_L$	$4\sqrt{n(n-1)}$
Focal Length	$F_L = \frac{F_D}{2}$	$2\sqrt{n(n-1)}$
Focus Point 1	$F1 = (x_{F1}, y_{F1})$	$(n + \sqrt{2n(n-1)}, n - 1 + \sqrt{2n(n-1)})$
Focus Point 2	$F2 = (x_{F2}, y_{F2})$	$(n - \sqrt{2n(n-1)}, n - 1 - \sqrt{2n(n-1)})$
Circle of Foci	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = D_F^2$	$(x - n)^2 + (y - n - 1)^2 = 4n(n - 1)$
Eccentricity	$e = \frac{F_L}{T_L}$	$\sqrt{2}$
HPSP Point 1	$HP1 = (x_{HP1}, y_{HP1})$	(n^2, n)
HPSP Point 2	$HP2 = (x_{HP2}, y_{HP2})$	$(1, -1)$
HPSP Diagonal $X[x]$	equation $y = X[x]$	$y = \frac{x}{n-1} - \frac{n}{n-1}$
HPSP Diagonal $Y[y]$	equation $x = Y[y]$	$x = (d_2 - d_1)y + d_1d_2$
HPSP Center Point	$HPC = (x_{HPC}, y_{HPC})$	$(\frac{n^2 + 1}{2}, \frac{n - 1}{2})$
HPSP Length	$HP_L = \frac{HP_D}{2}$	$\frac{(n + 1)\sqrt{n^2 - 2n}}{2}$
HPSP Circle	$(x - x_{HPC})^2 + (y - y_{HPC})^2 = HP_L^2$	$(x - \frac{n^2 + 1}{2})^2 + (y - \frac{n - 1}{2})^2 = \frac{(n^2 - 2n + 2)(n + 1)^2}{4}$
HPSP Distance	$HP_D = 2HP_L$	$(n + 1)\sqrt{n(n-2)}$

Figure 15. C000705 Summary table for trivial YB diagonal $b = b_d = n - 1$ and $c = n = d_2 = \text{integer}$.

14 The TSP Diagonals

Description	Notation	Equation
Hyperbola	<i>equation</i>	$xy = x + ny$ or $1 = \frac{1}{y} + \frac{n}{x}$
Divisors' Vertical	<i>equation</i>	$x = n$
Divisors' Diag. Asc.	<i>equation</i>	$x = y + n$
Divisors' Diag. Desc.	<i>equation</i>	$x - y + n$
Vertical Asymptote	<i>equation</i> $x = \text{constant}$	$x = n$
Horizontal Asymptote	<i>equation</i> $y = \text{constant}$	$y = 1$
Center Point	$C = (x_C, y_C)$	$(n, 1)$
Transverse Axis	<i>equation</i> $x = Y[y]$	$x = y + n - 1$
Conjugate Axis	<i>equation</i> $x = Y[y]$	$x = -y + n + 1$
Vertices Point 1	$V1 = (x_{V1}, y_{V1})$	$(n + \sqrt{n}, 1 + \sqrt{n})$
Vertices Point 2	$V2 = (x_{V2}, y_{V2})$	$(n - \sqrt{n}, 1 - \sqrt{n})$
Co-Vertices Point 1	$CV1 = (x_{CV1}, y_{CV1}) = (x_{V2}, y_{V1})$	$(n - \sqrt{n}, 1 + \sqrt{n})$
Co-Vertices Point 2	$CV2 = (x_{CV2}, y_{CV2}) = (x_{V1}, y_{V2})$	$(n + \sqrt{n}, 1 - \sqrt{n})$
Transverse Length	T_L	$\sqrt{2n}$
Conjugate Length	C_L	$\sqrt{2n}$
Circle of Vertices	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = TL^2$	$(x - n)^2 + (y - 1)^2 = 2n$
Focal Distance	$F_D = 2F_L$	$4\sqrt{n}$
Focal Length	$F_L = \frac{F_D}{2}$	$2\sqrt{n}$
Focus Point 1	$F1 = (x_{F1}, y_{F1})$	$(n + \sqrt{2n}, 1 + \sqrt{2n})$
Focus Point 2	$F2 = (x_{F2}, y_{F2})$	$(n - \sqrt{2n}, 1 - \sqrt{2n})$
Circle of Foci	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = D_F^2$	$(x - n)^2 + (y - 1)^2 = 4n$
Eccentricity	$e = \frac{F_L}{T_L}$	$\sqrt{2}$
HPSP Point 1	$HP1 = (x_{HP1}, y_{HP1})$	$\left(\frac{1 + 2n + \sqrt{1 + 4n}}{2}, \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4n}}{2}\right)$
HPSP Point 2	$HP2 = (x_{HP2}, y_{HP2})$	$\left(\frac{1 + 2n - \sqrt{1 + 4n}}{2}, \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 + 4n}}{2}\right)$
HPSP Diagonal X[x]	<i>equation</i> $y = X[x]$	$y = x - n$
HPSP Diagonal Y[y]	<i>equation</i> $x = Y[y]$	$x = y + n$
HPSP Center Point	$HPC = (x_{HPC}, y_{HPC})$	$\left(\frac{1 + 2n}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right)$
HPSP Length	$HP_L = \frac{HP_D}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{2(1 + 4n)}}{2}$
HPSP Circle	$(x - x_{HPC})^2 + (y - y_{HPC})^2 = HP_L^2$	$\left(x - \frac{1 + 2n}{2}\right)^2 + \left(y - \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{(1 + 4n)}{2}$
HPSP Distance	$HP_D = 2HP_L$	$\sqrt{2(1 + 4n)}$

Figure 16. C000705 Summary table with $b = b_d = 1$ and $c = n$ Integer numbers.

Below is a summary of all the parameters of the hyperbolas producing TSP diagonals.

Description	Notation	Equation
Hyperbola	<i>equation</i>	$xy = n(x + y)$ or $1 = \frac{n}{y} + \frac{n}{x}$
Divisors' Vertical	<i>equation</i>	$x = n$
Divisors' Diag. Asc.	<i>equation</i>	$x = y + n$
Divisors' Diag. Desc.	<i>equation</i>	$x - y + n$
Vertical Asymptote	<i>equation</i> $x = \text{constant}$	$x = n$
Horizontal Asymptote	<i>equation</i> $y = \text{constant}$	$y = n$
Center Point	$C = (x_C, y_C)$	(n, n)
Transverse Axis	<i>equation</i> $x = Y[y]$	$x = y$
Conjugate Axis	<i>equation</i> $x = Y[y]$	$x = -y + 2n$
Vertices Point 1	$V1 = (x_{V1}, y_{V1})$	$(2n, 2n)$
Vertices Point 2	$V2 = (x_{V2}, y_{V2})$	$(0, 0)$
Co-Vertices Point 1	$CV1 = (x_{CV1}, y_{CV1}) = (x_{V2}, y_{V1})$	$(0, 2n)$
Co-Vertices Point 2	$CV2 = (x_{CV2}, y_{CV2}) = (x_{V1}, y_{V2})$	$(2n, 0)$
Transverse Length	T_L	$\sqrt{2}n$
Conjugate Length	C_L	$\sqrt{2}n$
Circle of Vertices	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = TL^2$	$(x - n)^2 + (y - n)^2 = 2n^2$
Focal Distance	$F_D = 2F_L$	$4n$
Focal Length	$F_L = \frac{F_D}{2}$	$2n$
Focus Point 1	$F1 = (x_{F1}, y_{F1})$	$(n(1 + \sqrt{2}), n(1 + \sqrt{2}))$
Focus Point 2	$F2 = (x_{F2}, y_{F2})$	$(n(1 - \sqrt{2}), n(1 - \sqrt{2}))$
Circle of Foci	$(x - c)^2 + (y - b)^2 = D_F^2$	$(x - n)^2 + (y - n)^2 = 4n^2$
Eccentricity	$e = \frac{F_L}{T_L}$	$\sqrt{2}$
HPSP Point 1	$HP1 = (x_{HP1}, y_{HP1})$	$\left(\frac{n^2 + 2n + n\sqrt{n(n+4)}}{2}, \frac{n + \sqrt{n(n+4)}}{2}\right)$
HPSP Point 2	$HP2 = (x_{HP2}, y_{HP2})$	$\left(\frac{n^2 + 2n - n\sqrt{n(n+4)}}{2}, \frac{n - \sqrt{n(n+4)}}{2}\right)$
HPSP Diagonal X[x]	<i>equation</i> $y = X[x]$	$y = \frac{x}{n} - 1$
HPSP Diagonal Y[y]	<i>equation</i> $x = Y[y]$	$x = n(y + 1)$
HPSP Center Point	$HPC = (x_{HPC}, y_{HPC})$	$\left(\frac{n(n+2)}{2}, \frac{n}{2}\right)$
HPSP Length	$HP_L = \frac{HP_D}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{(n^2 + 1)n(n+4)}}{2}$
HPSP Circle	$(x - x_{HPC})^2 + (y - y_{HPC})^2 = HP_L^2$	$\left(x - \frac{n(n+2)}{2}\right)^2 + \left(y - \frac{n}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{(n^2 + 1)n(n+4)}{4}$
HPSP Distance	$HP_D = 2HP_L$	$\sqrt{(n^2 + 1)n(n+4)}$

Figure 17. C000705 Summary table with $b = b_d = n$ and $c = n$ Integer numbers.

14.1 Example TSP Diagonal

Figure 18. The TSP diagonal is brown. Because of the hyperbola $xy = x + 12y$ the TSP diagonal has the center at (12.5,0.5).

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Conflicts of Interest

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References

- [1] Babbage, Charles. (1791-1871) "Babbage's Difference Engine, Principle of the difference Engines", CHM Computer History Museum, available online at <https://www.computerhistory.org/babbage/howitworks>.
- [2] Belden, Otto. "Going's on of Otto's Pastimes", available online at <http://ottobelden.blogspot.com/2010/10/number-sequences-with-ms-excel-visual.html>.
- [3] Cox, David N. (2008) "Visualizing the Sieve of Eratosthenes". Notices of the American Mathematical Society. Volume 55, issue 5, page 579, available online at <https://www.ams.org/notices/200805/tx080500579p.pdf>.
- [4] Evard, Jean-Claude. (2018) "How to find central pairs of complementary divisors of n?", <https://www.researchgate.net/post/How-to-find-central-pairs-of-complementary-divisors-of-n>.
- [5] Gathen, Joachim & Gerhard, Jürgen. (1997). Fast Algorithms for Taylor Shifts and Certain Difference Equations. Proceedings of the International Symposium on Symbolic and Algebraic Computation, ISSAC. 40-47. 10.1145/258726.258745. Available online at file:///C:/Users/charl/Downloads/Fast_Algorithms_for_Taylor_Shifts_and_Certain_Diff.pdf.
- [6] Grime, James. (2013) "Prime Spirals - Numberphile", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iFuR97YcSLM>.
- [7] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252480>.

- [8] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Symbolic Conventions and Lexicon. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10127987>.
- [9] Kusniec, Charles (2023). The SOM Numbers (part I). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208029>.
- [10] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The TSP - Triangular Sieve of Primes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10155610>.
- [11] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Divisor Trek. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10128279>.
- [12] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Integers are only Primes and Composites. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419643>.
- [13] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Shift, Symmetry, and Asymmetry in Polynomial Sequences. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433336>.
- [14] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The Hyperbolic Sieve of Prime Numbers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419575>.
- [15] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The MHSP - Modular Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10109568>.
- [16] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The Polynomial Simplest Equations, the Symmetry Point, the Two Simplest Recurrence Equations, and the Method of Differences. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8434817>.
- [17] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Offset in Quadratics", EasyChair Preprint no. 4428, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/FQgX>.
- [18] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Quadratics Classification", EasyChair Preprint no. 4429, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/KRpp>.
- [19] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The Polynomial Simplest Equations, the Symmetry Point, the Two Simplest Recurrence Equations, and the Method of Differences", EasyChair preprint no. 4423, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/qr3P>.
- [20] Lo, Joseph. "Hyperbolic paraboloid", available online at http://www.math.ubc.ca/~cwsei/math200/graphics/hyperbolic_paraboloid.html.
- [21] Loh, Po-Shen. Daily Challenge with Po-Shen Loh. (2019) "Examples: A Different Way to Solve Quadratic Formulas", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XKBOXr3J-9Y>.
- [22] Mathematics, StackExchange. (2015) "Meaning of Rays in Polar Plot of Prime Numbers", available online at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/885879/meaning-of-rays-in-polar-plot-of-prime-numbers>.

- [23] Mathematics, StackExchange. (2016) "How to force prime numbers into a line?", available online at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/1291787/how-to-force-prime-numbers-into-a-line>.
- [24] Matiyasevich, Yuri and Stechkin, Boris. (1999) "A visual Sieve for Prime Numbers", available online at <https://logic.pdmi.ras.ru/~yumat/personaljournal/sieve/sieve.html>.
- [25] Medina, Miguel Ángel Morales (^DiAmOnD^). (2006) "142857: Un número realmente interesante", available online at <https://www.gaussianos.com/142857-un-numero-realmente-interesante/>.
- [26] Medina, Miguel Ángel Morales (^DiAmOnD^). (2013) "La sorprendente criba de la parábola", available online at https://www.gaussianos.com/la-sorprendente-criba-de-la-parabola/?utm_source=feedburner&utm_medium=feed&utm_campaign=Feed%3A+gaussianos+%28Gaussianos%29
- [27] Munafo, Robert. (1996-2020) "Sequence A002061, Hogben's Centered Polygonal Numbers", available online at <http://mrob.com/pub/seq/a002061.html>.
- [28] Munafo, Robert. (1996-2020) "Sequence A006542, $C(n, 3)C(n - 1, 3)/4$ ", available online at <http://mrob.com/pub/seq/a006542.html>.
- [29] OEIS Foundation Inc. (2021), "The On-Line Encyclopedia of integer Sequences". Published electronically at <http://oeis.org>.
- [30] Paris, Carlos. (2009) "Primal Chaos (Visualizations)", available online at <http://www.sievesofchaos.com/>.
- [31] Pegg, Ed Jr. (2006) "Prime Generating Polynomials, Math Games", available online at http://www.mathpuzzle.com/MAA/48-Prime%20Generating%20Polynomials/mathgames_07_17_06.html.
- [32] Pol, Omar Evaristo. (2001-2007), "Sobre el patrón de los números primos", available online at <http://www.polprimos.com/>.
- [33] Pol, Omar Evaristo. (2009-2012) "Links with illustrations", available online in the sequences <https://oeis.org/A027750> , <https://oeis.org/A056538> , <https://oeis.org/A193829> , <https://oeis.org/A212119>.
- [34] Ross, Michael M. (2007-2015) "Natural Numbers", available online at <http://www.naturalnumbers.org>.
- [35] Sacks, Robert. (2003-2007) "NumberSpiral.com", available online at <http://www.numberspiral.com/index.html>.
- [36] Sanderson, Grant (3Blue1Brown). (2019) "Why do prime numbers make these spirals?", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EK32jo7i5LQ>.
- [37] Sanderson, Grant (3Blue1Brown). (2023) "The Prime Number Race" - Numberphile, available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YAsHGOwB408>.

- [38] Schildbach, Wolfgang. "Patterns in prime numbers?", available online at <https://www.fermi.franken.de/wschildbach/primes.html#java>.
- [39] Stapel, Elizabeth. "Conics: Hyperbolas: Introduction", Purplemath, available from <https://www.purplemath.com/modules/hyperbola.htm>.
- [40] Stapel, Elizabeth. "Finding the Next Number in a Sequence: The Method of Common Differences", Purplemath, available from <https://www.purplemath.com/modules/nextnumb.htm>.
- [41] Unacademy Learning App, (?) "Rectangular Hyperbola", available online at <https://player.uacdn.net/lesson-raw/53KRIOKDC4WS1UKP233U/pdf/9971677413.pdf>.
- [42] Ventrella, Jeffrey. (2007) "Divisor Drips and Square Root Waves", available online at <http://www.divisorplot.com/>.
- [43] Viète, François. (1540-1603) "Formule de Viète", available online at https://edugemath.ch/1re/ch7/ma1-ch7-docs-cours/Ma1_Ch7-degre2_Viete.pdf and <http://serge.mehl.free.fr/chrono/Viete.html>.
- [44] Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, available online at <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Portal:Mathematics>.